

Digital impression – A Review.

Devikaa T.C, Priyanka Kumari, Shubhanshi Omar, Honey Jaiswal

Post Graduate Student, Department of Prosthodontics Crown & Bridge, Rama Dental College Hospital & Research Centre, Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh, India

Abstract

Dentistry has witnessed tremendous advancements in all its branches and newer devices have been continuously introduced in the practice. Digital impressions by intraoral scanning (IOS) have become an increasingly popular alternative to conventional impressions. They provide a 3D visualization of entire dentition in high resolution and creating record of hard and soft tissue to monitor oral diseases and condition. Impressions using scanners are more accurate, time efficient, decrease the patient's discomfort and make clinical procedures easier as compared to conventional technique. Intraoral scanning is regularly used by dentists and laboratories to design and fabricate esthetic and durable restorations while retaining maximum tooth structure, its use among dental infancy. CAD/CAM images can be used as a visual aid to improve self-care by demonstrating the health of a patient's oral cavity. A literature search was done to extract the studies on the advantages of digital impression over conventional impression, limitations of digital impression and recent advancements in intraoral scanners. After exclusion and inclusion criteria 30 articles were included for this narrative review. This article is a review of digital impression techniques over conventional impression techniques with different types of scanner and its key features.

Keyword: Digital, digital impression, conventional impression, scanner, virtual

Address of correspondence: T.C.Devikaa, Department of Prosthodontics Crown & Bridge, Rama Dental College Hospital & Research Centre, Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh, India

Email- devikaavineeth0021@gmail.com **Contact-** 9176063036. **DOI:** 10.5281/zenodo.5205375

Submitted: 30-Jul-2021 **Revised:** 4-Aug-2021 **Accepted:** 9-Aug-2021 **Published:** 15-Aug-2021

Introduction

Dental impression is a only procedure that records the oral tissues which are used for diagnostic purpose, treatment planning and prosthesis fabrication.^[1] Conventional impression has been used for many decades, it is associated with material preparation, increased chairside time, patient discomfort, laboratory preparation and risk of infection. Digital impressions were introduced in dentistry in mid 1980s.^[1]

Intraoral Scanners provide 3D visualization of real time intraoral images. The working principle of intraoral scanners include triangulation of light, active wavefront sampling, confocal imaging. The scanned images are processed into digital data and reflected as virtual model which is then transferred as stereolithography format (STL)

and designed in CAD software and milled in CAM software.^[4]

Intraoral scanner reduce the clinic time, enhance patient comfort and allow for visualizing the adequacy of the impression immediately, also minimize the material wastage and the ongoing cost. The intraoral scanner is composed of a handheld camera, computer, and software. The most widely used digital format is the open Standard Tessellation Language (STL) or locked STL-like. This format is a succession of triangulated surfaces in which each triangle is defined by three points and a normal surface. This technique uses a timed laser light directed at the structure and then reflected back to the camera where the data are captured and recorded.^[4]

Another type of intraoral scanner is parallel confocal imaging. This technique is based on acquisition of focused and defocused images from selected depths. Parallel confocal imaging can detect the sharpness of an area to infer distance to the object that is associated with the focal length of the lens.^[7] A tooth can then be reconstructed by consecutive images taken at different focuses and from altered angles around the object, allowing the clinician to directly place the handheld scanner on the tooth and increase stability. The sharpness of the area being scanned is directly related to the dexterity of the clinician, creating distortion and blur if the handheld scanner is not held appropriately.^[8]

The scanned model will remain virtual and they have the advantage of transfer. The dimensions of the impression may remain precise and prosthesis fabrication will have a accurate fit. The digital workflow can be used in all fields of dentistry including maxillofacial, implants and restorative dentistry^[9]. The old generation intraoral scanner has limited scanning range and use powder application for opacification, the latest scanner has a wide scanning range and can be used for full mouth cases. They have a open and closed system. Digital impression is a huge advancement especially in this pandemic era where risk of exposure to infection should be avoided^[9]

Search strategy:

A literature search was conducted in pubmed, embasse, google scholar using the key words digital impression, intraoral scanners, virtual, trueness, precision and using the Boolean operator intraoral and digitization, tooth or teeth, scan or digitization or digital impression. Articles were obtained on applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Additional articles were retrieved from google scholar by combining intraoral

scanner, digitization, conventional impression (Table 1 and 2).

Digital impression vs Conventional impression

Single tooth scanning- Studies have revealed that digital impression has been more accurate when compared to conventional technique in single tooth scanning but in case of detection of deep margin lines, subgingival margin preparation, bleeding there were seen some significant errors in reproducing the surface anatomy at the finish line region^[2]. The scanning in these regions are difficult due to accumulation of blood and presence of gingiva over subgingival finish line, hence light transmission is obscured which result in incomplete scanning^[2]

Quadrant arch scanning- Digital impression tend to show some deviation when the scanning span increases. In scenarios when the total occlusal convergence angle of the tooth decreases there is shown some significant errors in scanning.^[4] In short span bridges accuracy of digital impression is comparable and tend to be more accurate than conventional impression but in case of tight interproximal contact, steeper surfaces of teeth, gingival surfaces digital impressions showed greater amount of inaccuracies. In 4 unit bridges digital impression showed very high accuracy in terms of trueness or precision when compared to conventional impressions.^[2]

Whole arch scanning- Digital impression showed deviation in the posterior region when scanning the whole arch. The anterior segment shows less deviation when compared to posterior region.^[2] In case of crowding or inclination scanning resulted in inaccuracies, especially when there is pooling of saliva or metallic restoration due reflection of emitted light from the surface.^[2]

Advantages of digital impression:

Digital impression has a lot of advantages in many factors when compared to conventional impression. [12] It increases patient comfort, reduced working time and provide hassle free treatment. Since no impression material is placed in the patient's mouth, there is no issue of gagging and patient comfort is also increased, there is no worry of distortion of the material on removal. Once the dentist has learned to use the scanner, the impression can be taken in few minutes.

Accurate reproduction of surface anatomy and morphology is very important for the fabrication of prosthesis, digital impression reduces the burden on the operator and chairside time is also reduced. The newer technology enables us to replicate anatomy, morphology and even replicate the natural colour of the dentition. [14]

Impression tray must be sterilised and even the impression has to be disinfected on removal from patient mouth which even cause dimensional stability to the impression if immersed in the disinfectant solution for a longer duration. When impressions are made using intraoral scanner such problems are avoided and there is reduced risk to the operator and to the patient.

Digital impression provide us real time visualisation of 3D images, hence with reduced time and effort the impression can be rescanned or corrected. In conventional impression models have to be fabricated to check for any inaccuracies in the impression. [13] Impression made by intraoral scanner can be archived and saved for future references, unlike conventional impression cast/models need not have to be stored. Some intraoral scanners have cloud based technology hence enable to share the impression with the third party if needed. [13]

Real time visualisation of 3D images enables a proper treatment planning of the clinical

scenario in terms of abutment evaluation, calculating interarch space, pontic evaluation, evaluating functional and morphological design of the restoration, hence promising results can be achieved without any impression or fabrication of diagnostic models. [7] Merging the intraoral impression with the CT scan helps us in a comprehensive treatment planning for implants and maxillofacial reconstruction which enables proper treatment planning, virtual matching of natural colour tone of gingiva and tooth, helps in shade matching and determine the prognosis of the treatment. Digital impression can be used as search tool in disaster management for identifying the missing persons and in can also be used in forensic purposes for identification of the victim. [2,4,7]

Sterilisation of intraoral scanners:

When compared to conventional impression, intraoral scanner provide less exposure to pathogens by avoiding direct contact with the impression, pouring the cast and packaging the material. According to CDC classification, intraoral scanners have non-critical and semi-critical surfaces. The scanning wand, touch screen, and base are non-critical surface, disposable sleeves or tips which cover the sensor are semi-critical surfaces. All the non-critical surfaces can be cleaned with a disinfectant liquid that is approved by EPA. The non-critical surfaces must be cleaned first and then wiped with a guaze dipped in the disinfectant or cleaned with a premoistened disinfectant wipe. [17,18]

The semi-critical surfaces come into contact with oral cavity can be sterilised by using an autoclave or by using disposable sleeves or tips. Initially the sleeves are cleaned with soap water thoroughly and dried using a linen free paper towel and then autoclaved. Most of the scanner tips are removable, hence they can be autoclaved and reused. After

sterilisation, it is inspected for any damage or scratches, if in case any they should be discarded. It is also advisable to refer to the instructor's manual for disinfection protocol.^[16,17,18]

Conclusion:

Within the limitations of this review, it appears that, digital imaging is one of the crucial step for diagnostic purposes and short-span scanning. The accuracy of IOS systems is superior when compared to the accuracy of conventional impressions. Studies have shown that intraoral digital scanners are becoming integral of modern dentistry. Rescanning are quick, easy and inexpensive. Since the different IOS systems appear to have the potential to provide an outcome of superior accuracy without any statistically significant difference, no preference for a particular system can be made. Patient as well as operator prefers digital impression technique with higher level of acceptance and satisfaction.

References:

1. Yoshimasa Takeuchi, Hiroyasu Koizumi, Mika Furuchi, Yohei Sato, Chikahir, Ohkubo, and Hideo Matsumura. Use of digital impression systems with intraoral scanners for fabricating restorations and fixed dental prostheses. *J. Oral. Sci.* 2018; 60:1-7.
2. Dr. Jaafar Abduo, Dr. Mohamed Elseyoufi. Accuracy of Intraoral Scanners: A Systematic Review of Influencing Factors. *Eur. J. Prosthodont. Restor. Dent.* 2018; 26:101–121.
3. Bart Vandenberghe. The digital patient – Imaging science in dentistry. *Journal of Dentistry* 2018; 74:S21–S26.
4. Kazuhiko SUESE. Progress in digital dentistry: The practical use of intraoral scanners *Dental Materials Journal* 2020.
5. Alexander Schmidt , Leona Klussmann, Bernd Wöstmann and Maximiliane Amelie Schlenz. Accuracy of Digital and Conventional Full-Arch Impressions in Patients: An Update, *J. Clin. Med.* 2020; 9:688.
6. Hasan Kocaağaoğlu, Haydar Albayrak, Sezgi Cinel Sahin, Ayşegül Güteryüz Gürbulak, Evaluation of marginal adaptation in three-unit frameworks fabricated with conventional and powder-free digital impression techniques. *J Adv Prosthodont* 2019; 11:262-70.
7. Francesco Mangano, Andrea Gandolfi, Giuseppe Luongo and Silvia Logoza, Intraoral scanners in dentistry: a review of the current literature. *BMC Oral Health* 2017; 17:149.
8. Raphaël Richert, Alexis Goujat, Laurent Venet, Gilbert Viguie, Stéphane Viennot, Philip Robinson, Intraoral Scanner Technologies: A Review to Make a Successful Impression *Journal of Healthcare Engineering* 2017: 9.
9. Tim Joda, Fernando Zarone and Marco Ferrari, The complete digital workflow in fixed prosthodontics: a systematic review. *BMC Oral Health* 2017; 17:124.
10. Asher Chiu, Yen-Wei Chen , Juri Hayashi and Alireza Sadr, Accuracy of CAD/CAM Digital Impressions with Different Intraoral Scanner Parameters *Sensors* 2020; 20:1157.
11. Cristian Abad-Coronell, Od Pamela Valdiviezo Z2 and Od Belén Naranjo Y2, Intraoral Scanning Devices Applied in Fixed Prosthodontics. *ACTA SCIENTIFIC DENTAL SCIENCES* (ISSN: 2581-4893) 2019; 3:7.
12. Lidia Tordiglione, Michele De Franco, and Giovanni Bosetti, The Prosthetic Workflow in the Digital Era, *International Journal of Dentistry* 2016; 7.

13. Dr. Suresh S. Kamble, Dr. Ajit S. Jankar, Dr. Vidya A. Vaybase, Dr. Suraj Sonawane, Dr. Pratiksha Somwanshi et al. Digital dentistry: an overview on recent advancements in intraoral scanner Int. J. Adv. Res. 2009; 8:1244-1250.
14. Youn-Gyeong Moon and Kyung-Min Lee, Comparison of the accuracy of intraoral scans between complete-arch scan and quadrant scan, Moon and Lee Progress in Orthodontics 2020; 21:36.
15. Maximiliane Amelie Schlenz, Victoria Schubert, Alexander Schmidt, Bernd Wöstmann et al, Sabine Ruf Digital versus Conventional Impression Taking Focusing on Interdental Areas: A Clinical Trial Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health 2020; 17: 4725.
16. Ling ML, Ching P, Widaditaputra A, Stewart A, Sirijindadirat N. APSIC guidelines for disinfection and sterilization of instruments in health care facilities. Antimicrobial Res Infect Cont 2018; 7(1): 25.
17. Chidambaranathan AS, Balasubramaniam M. Comprehensive review and comparison of the disinfection techniques currently available in the literature. J Prosthodont. 2019; 28:e849–e856.
18. Alapatt JG, Varghese NM, Joy PT, Saheer MK, Correya BA. Infection Control In Dental Office: A Review. JDental Medical Sci 2016 Feb;15(2):10-15.
19. Dawood A, Purkayastha S, Patel S, MacKillop F, Tanner S. Microtechnologies in implant and restorative dentistry: a stroll through a digital dental landscape. Proc Inst Mech Eng H. 2010;224(6):789–96.
20. Ting-Shu S, Jian S. Intraoral digital impression technique: a review. J Prosthodont. 2015;4(24):313–21.
21. Joda T, Zarone F, Ferrari M. The complete digital workflow in fixed prosthodontics: a systematic review. BMC Oral Health. 2017;17(1):124.
22. Peumans M, Van Meerbeek B, Lambrechts P, Vanherle G. Porcelain veneers: a review of the literature. J Dent. 2000;28(3):163–77.
23. Little D. The Impact of Aesthetics in Restorative Treatment Planning. Dent Today. 2015;34(5):104, 106–07.
24. Gurel G, Morimoto S, Calamita MA, Coachman C, Sesma N. Clinical performance of porcelain laminate veneers: outcomes of the aesthetic pre-evaluative temporary (APT) technique. Int J Periodontics Restorative Dent. 2012;32(6):625–35.
25. Granell-Ruiz M, Fons-Font A, Labaig-Rueda C, Martinez-Gonzalez A, Roman Rodriguez JL, Solà-Ruiz MF. A clinical longitudinal study 323 porcelain laminate veneers. Period study from 3 to 11 years. Med Oral Patol Oral Cir Bucal. 2010;15(3):531–7.
26. Gurel G. Porcelain laminate veneers: minimal tooth preparation by design. Dent Clin N Am. 2007;51(2):419–31.
27. Buonocore MG. A simple method of increasing the adhesion of acrylic filling materials to enamel surfaces. J Dent Res. 1955;34(6):849–53.
28. Reshad M, Cascione D, Magne P. Diagnostic mock-ups as an objective tool for predictable outcomes with porcelain laminate veneers in esthetically demanding patients: a clinical report. J Prosthet Dent. 2008;99(5):333–9.
29. Santos DMD, Moreno A, Vechiato-Filho AJ, Bonatto LR, Pesquiera AA, Junior MCL, de Medeiros RA, da Silva EV, Goiato MC. The importance of the lifelike esthetic appearance of all-ceramic restorations on anterior teeth. Case Rep Dent. 2015.
30. Veneziani M. Ceramic laminate veneers: clinical procedures with a

- multidisciplinary approach. *Int J Esthet Dent.* 2017;12(4):426–48.
31. Gurrea J, Bruguera A. Wax-up and mock-up. A guide for anterior periodontal and restorative treatments. *Int J Esthet Dent.* 2014;9(2):146–62.
 32. Magne P, Belser UC. Novel porcelain laminate preparation approach driven by a diagnostic mock-up. *J Esthet Restor Dent.* 2004;16(1):7–16.
 33. Simon H, Magne P. Clinically based diagnostic wax-up for optimal esthetics: the diagnostic mock-up. *J Calif Dent Assoc.* 2008;36(5):355–62.
 34. Coachman C, Calamita MA, Sesma N. Dynamic documentation of the smile and the 2D/3D digital smile design process. *Int J Periodontics Restorative Dent.* 2017;37(2):183–93.
 35. Gherlone EF, Ferrini F, Crespi R, Gastaldi G, Capparé P. Digital impressions for fabrication of definitive all-on-four restorations. *Implant Dent.* 2015;24(1):125–9.
 36. Gherlone EF, Capparé P, Vinci R, Ferrini F, Gastaldi G, Crespi R. Conventional versus digital impressions for all-on-four restorations. *Int J Oral Maxillofac Implants.* 2016;31(2):324–30.
 37. Schmitter M, Seydler B. Minimally invasive lithium disilicate ceramic veneers fabricated using chairside CAD/CAM: a clinical report. *J Prosthet Dent.* 2012; 107(2):71–4.
 38. Gherlone EF, Mandelli F, Capparé P, Pantaleo G, Traini T, Ferrini F. A 3 years retrospective study of survival for zirconia-based single crowns fabricated from intraoral digital impressions. *J Dent.* 2014;42(9):1151–5.
 39. Cattoni F, Mastrangelo F, Gherlone EF, Gastaldi G. A New Total Digital Smile Planning Technique (3D-DSP) to Fabricate CAD-CAM Mockups for Esthetic Crowns and Veneers. *Int J Dent.* 2016.
 40. Seydler B, Schmitter M. Esthetic restoration of maxillary incisors using CAD/ CAM chairside technology: a case report. *Quintessence Int.* 2011;42(7):533–7.
 41. A.S. Persson, A. Oden, M. Andersson, G. Sandborgh-Englund, Digitization of simulated clinical dental impressions: virtual three-dimensional analysis of exactness, *Dent. Mater.* 25 (7) (2009) 929–936.
 42. Power J. Gypsum products and investments. In: Powers J, editor. *Craig's Restorative Dental Materials.* St Louis: Mosby; 2006. p. 313–36.
 43. Wöstmann B, Rehmann P, Balkenhol M. Influence of impression technique and material on the accuracy of multiple implant impressions. *Int J Prosthodont.* 2008;21(4):299–301.
 44. Goracci C, Franchi L, Vichi A, Ferrari M. Accuracy, reliability, and efficiency of intraoral scanners for full-arch impressions: a systematic review of the clinical evidence. *Eur J Orthod.* 2016;38(4):422–8.
 45. Logozzo S, Franceschini G, Kilpelä A, Caponi M, Governi L, Blois L. A comparative analysis of intraoral 3d digital scanners for restorative dentistry. *Int J Med Technol.* 2008;5(1).
 46. Ercus S, Chung E, McLaren E. Esthetics with minimal tooth preparation achieved through a digital approach. *Compend Contin Educ Dent.* 2013; 34(6):428–31.
 47. Lin WS, Zandinejad A, Metz MJ, Harris BT, Morton D. Predictable restorative work flow for computer-aided design/computer-aided manufacture fabricated ceramic veneers utilizing a virtual smile design principle. *Oper Dent.* 2015;40(4):357–63.
 48. Sancho-Puchades M, Fehmer V, Hämmerle C, Sailer I. Advanced smile diagnostics using CAD/CAM mock-ups. *Int J Esthet Dent.* 2015;10:374–91.

49. Wong KY, Esguerra RJ, Chia VAP, Tan YH, Tan KBC. Three-dimensional accuracy of digital static Interocclusal registration by three intraoral scanner systems. *J Prosthodont Off J Am Coll Prosthodont*. 2018;27(2):120–8.
50. Kattadiyil MT, Goodacre CJ, Lozada JL, Garbacea A. Digitally planned and fabricated mandibular fixed complete dentures. Part 2. Prosthodontic phase. *Int J Prosthodont*. 2015;28(2):119–23.
51. Lozada JL, Garbacea A, Goodacre CJ, Kattadiyil MT. Use of a digitally planned and fabricated mandibular complete denture for easy conversion to an immediately loaded provisional fixed complete denture. Part 1. Planning and surgical phase. *Int J Prosthodont*. 2014;27(5):417–21.
52. Hassan B, Gimenez Gonzalez B, Tahmaseb A, Greven M, Wismeijer D. A digital approach integrating facial scanning in a CAD-CAM workflow for complete-mouth implant-supported rehabilitation of patients with edentulism: a pilot clinical study. *J Prosthet Dent*. 2017;117(4):486–92.
53. Park J-M. Comparative analysis on reproducibility among 5 intraoral scanners: sectional analysis according to restoration type and preparation outline form. *J Adv Prosthodont*. 2016;8(5):354–62.

Table 1

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Last 10 years articles	Articles involving use of digital impressions in used as a surgical guide
Articles with numerous citations	Articles emphasizing more on digital impression usage in other fields other than dentistry.
Studies evaluating digital impression over conventional impression	Articles that does not have much citations

Table 2

Scanner	Company	Working principle	Scanning mode	Key features	indications
Cerec bluecam	Sirona bensheim, Germany (1985)	Triangulation of light	Short wavelength blue light emitting diode photography technology with titanium oxide powder coating	Powder application helps in light dispersion and produce accurate images	Single tooth /single quadrant
Cerec omnicam	Dentsply sirona Germany	Triangulation of light	Three dimensional images with real colour with real time videophotometry technology	3D images with natural colour and chairside milling unit	Fabrication of single crown, inlay, onlay, implant abutment and Scanning of scan body
Cerec primescan	Dentsply sirona Germany	Triangulation of light	Scanning depth upto 20 mm with photorealistic scanning and artificial intelligence	Higher scanning speed, increase scanning depth hence subgingival preparation can be scanned with greater accuracy	Full arch scanning, subgingival preparations

Shape trios	3shape, copenhagen, Denmark	Ultrafast optical sectioning and confocal microscopy	Video-photometry with red laser light	Telecentricity and Scanning speed of 3000 images per second	3D profile of soft tissue and hard tissue,
Planscan 2015	Planmeca, driven by E4D Technologies		Blue laser light with real time video streaming technology	Removable scanner tip with built in heater, captures hard and soft tissue of various translucencies	Inlays, onlays, crown and bridges
Lava COS	3M ESPE, seefeld, Germany	Active wavefront sampling	Continuous 3D video imaging in motion	Replication of finish line, automatic bite registration	Fixed partial denture cases
IOS Fastscan 2015	IOS technologies	Active triangulation	Camera moves with the wand, sheet of light sweeps across the surface of teeth which projects as 3D real time image	Eliminates hand movement distortion, depth of focus and surface resolution is good	Monolithic and IPS EMAX crown and bridge
3D Progress 2015	MHT (Medical High Technologies) S.p.A (IT) and created by MHT Optic Research AG (CH)	Confocal microscope principle with Moire effect	Internal accelerometer helps to rotate, zoom the 3D scanned model	Smart pixel sensor, real time automatic stitching, special optical system to reach the end of jaws	Full arch, single tooth scan, implant abutment scanning (powder coating required)
Bluescan-I	Austrian research institute	Active stereoscopic vision principle	Two video cameras that record stereoscopic 3D images	Anti-fogging, Anti shake protection, smallest scanner, USB connection	Reduced mouth opening scenarios, posterior tooth scanning
Cara i500 2018	Kulzer in partnership with Medit	Cloud based workflow management	Two high speed cameras, video based scan, open system	High resolution coloured scan, integrated cloud system (data exchange easier)	Single custom abutment, veneer, 3 to 5 unit implant bridge, implant guide
Condor	Remedent Inc.	Cloud based workflow technology		Compare panoramic x-ray with intraoral scanner, hyper realistic colours, disinfectable and small handpiece, detection of margin line	Full arch, inlay, onlay, crowns and bridges, reduced mouth opening scenario